

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation

This article is about the appropriate use of modern technologies in learning and teaching English and the teacher's self-reflection, sense of responsibility, introduction of innovations into lessons, ensuring that the lesson is interesting and lively.

Keywords: innovation, technology, efficiency, specialization, information and communication, telecommunications.

Аннотация

Данная статья посвящена целесообразному использованию современных технологий в обучении и преподавании английского языка, а также саморефлексии учителя, чувству ответственности, внедрению инноваций в уроки, обеспечению интересного и увлекательного содержания урока.

Ключевые слова: инновации, технологии, эффективность, специализация, информационно-коммуникационные технологии, телекоммуникации.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola ingliz tilini o'rganish va o'rgatishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan o'rinli foydalanish va o'qituvchining o'z-o'zini aks ettirishi, mas'uliyatni his etishi, darsga yangilik kiritishi, darsning qiziqarli va jonli o'tishini ta'minlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsiyalar, texnologiya, samaradorlik, ixtisoslashuv, axborot va aloqa, telekommunikatsiya.

The new era imposes new tasks and a number of responsibilities on modern teachers. With the advent of modern technology, the tradition of teaching English has changed significantly. On December 10, 2012, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov adopted a resolution PQ-1875, "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages". According to this resolution, foreign language teachers were charged with the responsibility of introducing advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information and

communication technologies and preparing the younger generation to be fluent in foreign languages.

The resolution consists of several paragraphs, and it is precisely the ninth paragraph of the resolution that discusses in detail the use of innovative technologies.

According to the ninth paragraph of the resolution, “The National Television and Radio Company of Uzbekistan, the State Committee for Communications, Informatization and Telecommunication Technologies, the Press and Information Agency of Uzbekistan, and the National Information Agency of Uzbekistan, taking into account the interests and concerns of children and youth, shall ensure the following: To prepare and broadcast programs on teaching children and adolescents foreign languages on television, including local TV channels, and to regularly show popular science, foreign fiction and animation films dedicated to the history and culture of other peoples, world science and technology, with subtitles in the Uzbek language; Due to the fact that the “ZiyoNet” network significantly increases the access of educational institutions to international educational and knowledge resources, enriches its resource center with multimedia resources, applications for personal computers and mobile devices, as well as publishes educational and fiction literature in English, newspapers and magazines decorated with specialized illustrations, and organizes special columns and applications for them” [1, 2b], all English teachers are now beginning to feel the need to use technologies to further revitalize their lessons.

Currently, the importance of learning English in Uzbekistan is becoming much higher than before. A number of English language specialists are implementing new methods and ways of learning English. This will certainly increase the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages.

Using technologies, There are several unique advantages of teaching. In addition, it greatly increases the efficiency of the teaching system and, in turn, helps the language learner to keep up with the times and strive for progress.

Technology is gradually replacing traditional teaching.

Today, television programs are regularly broadcasting a number of new programs and shows that help teach English. Of course, the use of modern technologies in any foreign language lessons, such as computers, radios, CDs, and DVDs, will further advance the educational process and allow the younger generation to learn foreign languages faster.

During English lessons, some teachers' lack of knowledge and lack of use of technology leads to some boredom among students. For this reason, in order not

to dampen the student's enthusiasm, the use of technology and at least a computer during the lesson will further increase the student's interest. After all, educational materials prepared according to the student's age, interests, abilities, and mastery of the lessons will definitely be effective. On the contrary, if we teachers do not select educational materials based on these requirements, if we show elementary school students videos, songs or texts with complex words or show them through multimedia, computers, and if we show middle and upper school or group students educational materials with very simple texts, the students' interest in learning the language will gradually fade away and they will not master the lessons. This, in turn, can lead to a decrease in grades and a loss of respect for the teacher in the eyes of the students. Therefore, it follows that the main task is not just to use technologies during the lesson, but to be able to apply them in their place and ensure that the use of technologies serves to increase student knowledge. According to the current CEFR, the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), it is important to use technology effectively and appropriately during lessons on the four English language skills (writing, reading, listening, speaking). For example, there are specific rules for playing audio texts in listening and comprehension lessons. The main goal is for the learner to understand the audio material they are listening to and be able to analyze it without difficulty. To do this, first of all, prepare the environment for playing the audio material,

in which the listeners should ensure a calm environment, the teacher should pay attention to the quality of the audio being played and the good working of the amplifiers, and the exercises to be done before and after the audio should be ready, and the learners should be provided with handouts.

Once all the requirements have been met, the teacher can start playing the audio material to the learners. The playback should be carried out at least twice, otherwise the language learners may not understand the topic and may not be able to correctly perform the exercises to be done after listening to the audio material.

Also, when using technology in speaking and writing, it is a very effective method to use multimedia to show videos, films, and clips to students during the lesson and discuss them. In this case, vocabulary familiar to students should be used, new and complex words should be explained, and after completing exercises related to new words, video material can be shown. To implement this process, it is important to have a quiet, noise-free environment, a comfortable and clean classroom, the possibility of everyone watching, and to check that the sound

amplifiers are working. Before showing the video, the students should talk about the topic of the video to be shown, conduct questions and answers, and only after making sure that the students are really interested in this topic should the video be shown.

After the video is over, the teacher should be interested in the students' opinions about the video and do exercises. When these stages are carried out correctly, these lessons will certainly contribute greatly to the increase in students' interests and knowledge. It follows that the role of modern technologies in further enriching our lessons, in attracting students' interest, and in enriching their knowledge is incomparable. And the ability to use them correctly and appropriately is the main guarantee of our success.

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